

A Novel Multi-Scale Digital Image Correlation Approach for Monitoring Stable Skin-Stringer Delamination Growth in Post-buckled Composite Panels

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From Fuselage to Single-Stringer Specimen

**Rear Fuselage
Section**

Fuselage Panel

**Single-Stringer
Specimen**

Butt-joint Single-Stringer Specimen

Tracking Delamination Growth in Post-Buckling

Post-buckling
deformations

Research Objective

Experimental tracking of skin-stringer delamination growth in post-buckled composite panels.

Current Challenge

Experimental methods cannot continuously capture skin-stringer delamination growth in detail during post-buckling.

Why It Matters

Lack of detailed data limits calibration and validation of advanced numerical damage models.

Opportunity

High-fidelity experimental data can improve prediction accuracy, supporting certification of composite airframe post-buckling designs.

Outline

- ✓ **Design of Experiment**
- ✓ **Monitoring Methodology**
- ✓ **Results**
- ✓ **Conclusions & Future Work**

Design of Experiment: Specimen

Component	Material
Skin	UD AS4D/PEKK
Web	UD AS4D/PEKK
Filler	SCRIP CF/PEKK

DoE Objective:

Dimensions, layups and boundary conditions were optimized using FEA to maximize stable skin-stringer delamination growth.

Design of Experiment: FEM Setup

Element Types	Color
SC8R	
C3D8I	
C3D6	

FE Software: Abaqus 2023

Model Details:

- Mesh seed size: 1.25mm
- Local mesh refinement at the stringer
- Total elements: 869,568
 - ✓ Laminated components: SC8R elements
 - ✓ Filler: C3D8I and C3D6 elements
- Superficial resin layer on OML side explicitly modeled (SC8R elements)

Design of Experiment: Boundary Conditions

Simply-supported web
($U_2 = 0$)

Clamped ends

Aluminum blocks
as end tabs

Fixture enforcing a
simply-supported web.

Design of Experiment: Loading

Quasi-static application

Displacement control @ 0.04 mm/min

Design of Experiment: Damage Growth Using VCCT

Design of Experiment: Damage Growth Using VCCT

Strain Concentrations at Delamination Fronts

Indicator 1: Minimum in-plane principal strain on the Outer Mold Line (OML) surface

Indicator 2: Shear strain on the OML surface relative to a system aligned with the stringer

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Monitoring Methodology: DIC-based Crack Front Estimation

Validation: C-scans of the damage are acquired at different load levels and compared to DIC-based crack front estimates.

Global/Local DIC: Multi-Scale Pattern Design

Target feature size: $\sim 5\text{px}$

Global DIC { Resolution: $2048 \times 2448\text{ px}$
Field of View: $256 \times 305\text{ mm}$

Global feature

Local DIC { Resolution: $2160 \times 4096\text{ px}$
Field of View: $34 \times 65\text{ mm}$

Local feature

Global/Local DIC: Experimental Setup

Global/Local DIC: Fields of View

C-Scan Data: Reference for Validating Crack Front Monitoring

Detailed information on damage morphology (area, location, and depth) is obtained at different instances during the stable crack growth process.

High-fidelity reference measurements for validating DIC-based crack front monitoring.

Dolphicam 2

C-Scan Data: Damage Evolution with Increasing Load

Validation of the DIC-based Crack Front Monitoring Method

Validation of the DIC-based Crack Front Monitoring Method

Validation of the DIC-based Crack Front Monitoring Method

Enhanced Damage Quantification via Crack Front Monitoring

Conclusions & Future Work

- ✓ **Developed** and **validated** a novel DIC-based method for monitoring skin-stringer delamination growth in post-buckled composite panels.
- ✓ Enabled **continuous crack front tracking** during testing, advancing damage quantification beyond current standard approaches.
- ✓ The resulting data will **support validation of a high-fidelity numerical model**.
- ✓ The method will next be applied to a post-buckled **5-stringer panel**, representative of an actual airframe structure, to further demonstrate its capabilities.

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